

SMILE

**SUPPORTING MENTAL HEALTH IN YOUNG PEOPLE:
INTEGRATED METHODOLOGY FOR CLINICAL
DECISIONS AND EVIDENCE-BASED INTERVENTIONS**

From 01-05-2023 to 31-10-2026 (42 Months)

EU Contribution: €6,018,376.25

15 partners from 9 European countries

www.horizonsmile.eu

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SMILE will implement and validate its AI-tools, gamified scenarios and services through real-life strategic case studies in seven European countries: the United Kingdom, Germany, Cyprus, Poland, Slovenia, Spain, and Italy. This extensive validation process is scheduled to reach Technology Readiness Level 7.

Literature review

Clinical trials

Living Labs

Focus groups

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